

Hydrogen Reduction of Bauxite Residue Pellets and Effect of Calcite Addition

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Keywords: Bauxite residue, hydrogen reduction, thermogravimetry, mayenite

Abstract

The utilization of bauxite residue (BR) through iron oxide reduction and leachable alumina phase formation by hydrogen reduction were studied experimentally. Three different types of pellets were made: one from bauxite residue, and the other two via calcite addition with varying CaCO₃ amounts. All pellets were isothermally reduced by H₂ gas in a thermogravimetry furnace at constant temperature under fixed hydrogen flow rate and retention times. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), coupled with Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), were used for the phase and microstructural analysis. It was found that the formation of dominant phases during reduction is dependent on the reduction temperature and the quantity of CaCO₃ addition. The relative intensity of iron is constant for all reduced pellets at constant reduction temperature. There is no mayenite phase in the reduced BR pellets, but with the addition of calcite, a small amount of mayenite phase starts to appear, which increases with more calcite addition. In addition, similar metallic iron recoveries were observed for all reduced pellets, while the calcite-added ones had better composition for further alumina recovery.

1 Introduction

Bauxite is the main raw material for alumina production. Alumina is produced from the bauxite ore via hydrometallurgical process known as Bayer process, where bauxite ore is digested in caustic solution at high pressure to dissolve the alumina content. Almost all alumina producers around the globe uses the Bayer process for alumina production from bauxite ores [1][2][3]. However, an insoluble fraction separated during the Bayer process as a byproduct known as red mud or bauxite residue (BR). This residue is not easy to utilize due to its high pH, fine particle size, and high sodium content. In 2015 it was reported that 4.5 billion tons of BR have been stockpiled worldwide [4][5]. However, BR contains many valuable minerals like iron, aluminum, titanium, and REEs, which will make it as a

secondary resources in future [6][7][3]. Iron and alumina are the major constituents of BR, recovery of these two elements will decrease the residue volume largely. According to previous studies most of the iron recovery from BR were done by carbothermic reduction process [8][9][7][10]. During carbothermic reduction, large amounts of CO₂ are generated which is a prime concern. Using hydrogen reductant as a substitute of carbon is a more sustainable recovery process as it ensures no direct CO₂ during the reduction process, as long as hydrogen is produced using renewable energy. Valorization of BR using hydrogen reduction has been proposed by HARARE project in EU. The HARARE Project was started in 2021 and is a consortium of universities, research institutes and industrial companies from Norway, Greece, Germany and Belgium to recover metal production using ecofriendly means via BR valorization [11].

Unfortunately, very limited research has been done for the hydrogen reduction of BR[12][1][13]. Pilla et al, [13] studied the low-temperature hydrogen reduction of BR+NaOH pellets for Fe₂O₃ conversion to Fe₃O₄ and the formation of sodium aluminate phase. The result shows that the conversion of Fe₂O₃ to Fe₃O₄ is around 96 %. One of the previous studies in HARARE was on the agglomeration of BR-calcite pellets [14] and further hydrogen reduction of these pellets for iron and alumina recovery indicated that the alumina in the BR converted to calcium aluminate (mayenite) phase and recovery of alumina in soda leaching process is around 87 % [1]. Formation of mayenite is highly desirable as it has the highest leachability among other calcium aluminate phase in Na₂CO₃ leaching process [15][16]. This work focuses on hydrogen reduction behaviour (kinetics of reduction) of BR pellets, and BR-calcite pellets and their phases formation with similar reduction conditions. The difference compared to the previous HARARE studies [1][12] is studying low calcite additions for further process optimization.

2 Experimental procedure

The overall experimental flow sheet of this work is presented in Figure 1. The applied characterization methods for different materials are also given in this Figure.

Figure 1: Overview of experimental procedure and applied characterization methods

3 Materials and preparation

BR and calcite (CaCO₃) were used as starting materials. The BR provided by Mytilineos S.A. (formerly known as aluminum of Greece) and CaCO₃ from Omya S.A. Norway. These raw materials were dried in an oven overnight at 100 ±5 °C. Then the dried materials were deagglomerated and sieved below 500 µm. BR and CaCO₃ were mixed with varying CaCO₃ percentage. Mixture 1 contains BR and 10 wt. % of CaCO₃ and mixture 2 contains BR and 30 wt. % CaCO₃. These materials were mixed in Erich mixture for homogenization about 30 mins with 300 revolution per minute (rpm). After mixing, these materials were pelletized in a disc pelletizer via 10 wt.-% water addition. Three types of pellets were made as BR pellets (without calcite addition), BR + 10 wt.-% CaCO₃ pellets and BR + 30 wt.-% CaCO₃ Pellets. These Green pellets were dried overnight in oven at 100 °C. Hereafter BR pellets, BR + 10 % CaCO₃ pellets and BR + 30 % CaCO₃ pellets are named BR, BR+10Cal and BR+30Cal, respectively.

3.1 Hydrogen reduction of pellets

The dried pellets were reduced in a thermogravimetry (TG) furnace for kinetic study of reduction. The schematic view of the TG furnace is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic view of TG furnace (A) crucible (B) overall furnace

In Figure 2 schematic view of the furnace is divided into two parts. First one is the schematic drawing of crucible and second one is the overall furnace view. As shown in Figure 2(A), the crucible is a hollow cylinder, gas purged from the top, and it passes through the sample bed and goes out at the top of the crucible to off gas system. Pellets were placed on an alumina porous plug at the bottom of the crucible. The purpose of using alumina porous plug is to attain a proper gas flow through the pellets bed. In Figure 2(B), the crucible was hung with weight balance for the instantaneous weight measurement during reduction. One thermocouple was inserted inside the pellets bed (in the middle), and another was located on the furnace wall. The target temperature was set based on the two thermocouples reading. Weight balance, flow meter device, off gas analyzer and thermocouples were connected to data logger and the data logger to computer.

The heating, cooling and reduction profiles were same for all pellets. The pellets were heated in presence of argon (Ar) to the targeted temperature (1000 ± 10 °C) on $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ heat rate with argon gas flow of $1\text{NI}/\text{min}$. The calcite in the pellets was decomposed at temperatures below 1000 °C and when the set point temperature reached, there no remaining calcite (all converted to CaO) in the samples. This was confirmed by the absence of mass loss observations. Hence, after getting stable weight hydrogen introduction was started. During the hydrogen reduction cycle, pellets were reduced in presence of H_2 gas for 90 min with a flow rate of $4\text{NI}/\text{min}$. Cooling was done by purging Ar ($1\text{NI}/\text{min}$) on the reduced pellets to avoid oxidation of the reduced metallic iron.

3.2 Characterization

The mineralogical analysis of the raw materials and reduced pellets were carried out using the X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique (Bruker D8 A25 DaVinciTM, Karlsruhe, Germany) with the CuK α radiation and 2 θ diffraction angle range from 15 to 75° with step size 0.02°. A crystallographic database and EVA software were used for the diffraction analysis of the phases. For XRD analysis, these materials were powdered in a ring mill for 45 s at a revolution per minute (rpm) 800. The microstructural analysis of reduced pellets was obtained by using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Zeiss ultra 55LE, Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany), and the elemental analysis and mapping were by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) (Bruker, AXS, microanalysis GmbH, Berlin, Germany). The raw materials elemental analysis was done using the X-ray fluorescence (XRF) technique (Thermo fisher, Degerfors laboratorium AB, Sweden).

The mineralogical phase analysis of BR is presented later in the next section and indicated that iron is present in BR mostly in hematite and goethite phase. Aluminium is present in BR both in simple hydroxide (diaspore) and complex oxides (Cancrinite, katoite, and sodalite). Titanium is present in anatase, perovskite phase and calcium in calcite. These oxides are the major constituents of BR.

The chemical composition of the BR and limestone are presented in Table 1. A major fraction of the weight in BR is composed of iron oxide and alumina. Limestone consists mostly of CaO with some fractions of SiO₂ and MgO.

Table 1: XRF elemental analysis of BR and limestone

Materials/oxides	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	MnO	MgO	Na ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	LOI
BR	22	8.8	40.71	0.09	0.08	0.23	3.1	0.11	0.95	7.1	5	12.4
Limestone	0.9	52.7	0.15	0.12	0.95	0.01	0.06	2.07	0.03	42.6

4 Results and Discussion

Figure 3 represents the weight reduction concerning hydrogen reduction time for BR, BR+10Cal, and BR+30Cal pellets. As shown in Figure 3 for all pellets weight reduction became flattened after 30 min of reduction, which indicates that reduction is almost completed. The weight reduction curves show that for all the three pellets there is an initial stage with very high rate of mass reduction, which is followed by a significantly lower reduction rate. The initial rate of reduction was found to be very close for all the pellets. The total weight loss during reduction of BR, BR+10Cal and BR+30Cal pellets are around 12.9 % ,11.9 % and 10.5 %, respectively. BR reduced pellets have higher weight loss due to higher amounts of iron oxide than the other two oxide pellets. This is because, with same weight of 3 pellets, BR has a high percentage of iron oxide as compared to BR+10Cal and BR+30Cal pellets.

4.1 Rate and extent of reduction

Fraction reduced with respect to time of 3 different types of pellets are presented in Figure 4. Fraction reduced was calculated as:

$$Fraction\ reduced(X) = \frac{Actual\ weight\ loss(\Delta w)}{Oxygen\ mass\ in\ iron\ oxide\ at\ initial(w_{in})} \tag{1}$$

Where, X is the fraction reduced, Δw is the actual weight loss during reduction (oxygen removed) for a given time, and w_{in} is the oxygen mass present in iron oxide at initial.

Figure 3: Weight reduction with time for three different types of pellets

Rate of reduction is calculated as per the equation 2.

$$Rate\ of\ reduction = \left(\frac{Y(g)}{t(min)}\right) \left(\frac{1\ mol\ O}{16\ g\ O}\right) \left(\frac{1\ min}{60\ sec}\right) = \left(\frac{Y}{t}\right) \left(\frac{1}{960}\right) \left(\frac{mol}{sec}\right) \tag{2}$$

Where Y is the oxygen removed during initial stage of reduction, t is the time required for initial stage of reduction. By using equation 2 the rate of reduction of BR, BR+10Cal and BR+30Cal were $7.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $3.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $3.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ respectively. From the above results, it was found that the rate of reduction is faster for BR pellets as compared to BR calcite pellets.

Fraction reduction goes above 80 % within a short reduction time. Majority of iron present in the pellets is from Fe_2O_3 and their reduction reaction with hydrogen is as follows:

Figure 4: Fraction reduced vs time for three different types of pellets

As shown in Figure 4, the initial reduction rate is about 90 % for BR reduced pellets however for BR calcite added pellets it was lower which is around 70 to 75 %. The rate of reduction in BR reduced pellets is higher due to more amount of Fe_2O_3 to Fe reduction but in case of BR calcite added pellets the activity of iron oxide decreases by the formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ during heating. As per thermodynamics calculation presented in equation 4 and 6, formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ is more favorable than $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_2\text{SiO}_7$ at 1000°C and the formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ during heating is supported by high temperature sintering of BR calcite pellets from our previous work [14].

4.2 The phase evolution during reduction

Figure 5 represents the phase analysis of BR and reduced pellets. Metallic iron (Fe), perovskite (CaTiO_3), gehlenite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_2\text{SiO}_7$), corundum (Al_2O_3), nepheline ($\text{Al}_4\text{Ca}_{0.03}\text{K}_{0.54}\text{Na}_{3.24}\text{O}_{16}\text{Si}_4$) and mayenite ($\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$) are the major phases of reduced pellets. All iron oxides in the dry pellets were reduced to metallic iron which corresponds to XRD result. There is no unreduced iron oxide phase found in XRD. Aluminum was present in BR dry pellets as diaspor, however, it converted to corundum phase after reduction. This is due to high temperature phase transformation of diaspor to corundum. There is no corundum phase present in BR+10Cal reduced pellets. Alumina and silica present in dry pellets react with CaO at high temperature to form gehlenite via reaction (5). After the stoichiometric gehlenite formation with silica that were present in sample, the remaining alumina reacts with CaO to form mayenite via reaction (5) which was correlated to XRD results. There is no mayenite phase in the BR reduced pellets, however, mayenite phase formation increases with increasing CaCO_3 addition. Gibbs free energy of formation of gehlenite, mayenite and $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ calculated

by using Factsage 8.1 are presented below and from thermodynamics point of view the reactions occur.

The Gibbs energy of mayenite, was not found in literature and thermodynamics tables, therefore a database developed for calcium-aluminate slags was used [17]. Formation of more mayenite is more favorable at pellets with higher calcite addition which may be due to the lower free energy of formation (equation 4 and 5) and the limited amount of SiO₂ in the pellets. From our previous study it was observed that formation of mayenite is more favorable during hydrogen reduction as compared to gehlenite[12].

Figure 5: XRD of reduced pellets

4.3 Microstructural properties

The microstructural image analysis of BR reduced pellets and BR+30Cal reduced pellets are shown in Figure 6. The phases marked in the Figure 6 were confirmed by using EDS point and area analysis. In BR reduced pellets, the metallic iron particles were distributed everywhere in the matrix and in some area the iron particles are sintered as the reduction occurs at high temperature. Al in reduced BR pellets is present in corundum phase, which is shown in Figure 6(b). Other dominant phases found in BR reduced pellet was the same as BR+10Cal and BR+30Cal reduced pellets, except mayenite. The mayenite phase present in BR+10Cal and BR+30Cal reduced pellets has a higher amount in BR+30Cal, which agrees with XRD results.

Figure 6: SEM image of (a) BR+30Cal reduced pellets (b)BR reduced pellets

The elemental mapping of BR reduced pellets and BR+30Cal reduced pellets are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8, respectively. As seen, iron is present separately without overlapping with oxygen, signifying that iron oxide is fully reduced to metallic iron which agrees with XRD results above. In BR reduced pellets aluminium and oxygen are overlapping in some area, which indicates the existence of Al_2O_3 phase in the reduced sample. In some area calcium, titanium and oxygen is overlapped, this phase is perovskite which shown in both Figure 7 and 8.

Figure 7: Elemental mapping of BR reduced pellets

In BR+30Cal reduced sample, calcium, aluminium, and oxygen coexist in some area which manifested the existence of mayenite ($\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$) as shown in Figure 8. This phase is also found in XRD as well as EDS elemental analysis.

Figure 8: Elemental mapping of BR+30Cal reduced pellets

5 Conclusions

Hydrogen reduction of BR and BR-calcite pellets were carried out and the products were characterized. The results are summarized as below

- The initial rate of reduction of BR and BR-Calcite pellets is almost the same, while BR-Calcite pellets have a faster in latter stage of reduction.
- The extent of reduction in the initial stage is higher for BR pellet (about 90 %) and complete reduction occurs in shorter time compared to BR-Calcite pellets.
- The rate of reduction is higher for BR pellets during initial stage of reduction, which may be due to higher amount of Fe_2O_3 to Fe reduction, however this is not in case of BR calcite pellets.
- The initial rate of reduction is lower for calcite added pellets, due to formation of some $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ phase during heating cycle. Formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ phase during heating cycle decreases the activity of the reactant phase during reduction.
- With increasing calcite addition, mayenite phase becoming more favorable compared to gehlenite during hydrogen reduction due to lower free energy of formation and limited SiO_2 present.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958307. This publication represents only the authors' views, exempting the Community from any liability. The Harare Project website is <https://h2020harare.eu/>

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